

Preparation for expert interviews:
An investigation of the potential of aikido, a Japanese martial art,
for intercultural encounters and communication

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1. Disclaimer

Informed consent:

- in writing
- on recording

2. Purpose

My name is Greet De Baets, I am a researcher at Ghent University and I am conducting academic/doctoral research on aikido-based intercultural communication training.

The purpose is to learn what you consider to be principles of aikido on and off the mat. It is important to know this from you, an expert in aikido, in [location] in [year].

3. Topic list

A semistructured interview:

Section	Topic	Question	Probing	Internal comment
A. Martial biography	Lineage	Which school of aikido do you belong to?		Lineage is the line of teachers tracing back to the founder of aikido, o'sensei, Ueshiba Morihei.
	Expertise	What is your grade?		Dan grades (black belt grades) and status grades in the Japanese martial schools' system.
	Broadness	What other martial arts do/did you practice?	So why aikido?	
B. Aikido principles	Facts	What are the key principles of aikido?		Important for the terminology and coding categories.
	Opinions	How do you interpret them?		

	Challenge for completeness	What are the inconsistencies or shortages in the aikido principles, if any?		
	Peace	How come a martial art can be an art of harmony?	What does fighting mean in aikido? What does winning mean in aikido?	
	Target domain	How have you used aikido off the mat?	[If the experience was a physical self-defense] Has aikido inspired you in other ways?	To test a possible link to communication and behavior.
	Intangible aspect	What intangible/spiritual value does aikido have for you?		
C. Demography	Whereabouts now and before	Where have you lived?	What is your experience with intercultural encounters?	To test a possible link to intercultural communication and behavior.
	[If no intercultural experience] a case-based question	If [I present an intercultural case] you suddenly need to complete a two-year assignment on another continent where you don't know the language, what would you do?	What is the link between an aikido blackbelt and a communication blackbelt?	
D. Conclusion	Uniqueness?	Some say that aikido is unique: what are your thoughts on that?		
	Anything else?	Is there anything else you consider important or relevant?		

4. The end of the interview

Leaving with a bridge towards future communication: e.g. to ask for a second interview, to give feedback on the results (a short report).

Snowballing...